

Textual Analysis of Social Media Framing of the 2024 Edo State Gubernatorial Election Campaigns

Malvis Chekwube Eke

Department of Mass Communication
University of Benin, Edo State, Nigeria
malviseke4@gmail.com; +234803-181-4955
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15871069>

Abstract

The researcher conducted this study to do a textual analysis of social media framing of the 2024 Edo State gubernatorial election campaigns. The rationale of the study was to ascertain how social media users framed the elections in select social media platforms. The study is grounded on the framing theory. A textual analysis method was employed, with textual analysis guide used to gather data. The key findings indicated that the dominant frames identified in the election campaigns included negative campaigning, praise singing, battle for the future of Edo State and critiques of candidates. In conclusion, social media played a crucial role in the 2024 Edo gubernatorial election campaigns, with their framing impacting the electorate's views and engagement. Key recommendations are that political parties and political campaigns organisers should focus on framing issues and candidates in a positive and constructive light, prioritising policy discussions over personal attacks, amongst others.

Keywords: Social Media, Framing, Edo State, Gubernatorial Election, Campaign, Framing Theory

Introduction

The emergence of social media as a central pillar of modern political campaigns has significantly reshaped the landscape of electoral communication. Traditionally, political campaigns were primarily conducted through face-to-face interactions, mass media outlets such as television, radio and newspapers, and more recently, through blogs and websites (Santas, Asemah & Jumbo, 2020; Olaoye, Enyindah & Asemah, 2022; Omoevah, Oladele & Asemah, 2022; Egwa, Obaje & Asemah, 2024). However, the digital age has seen a monumental shift in how election campaigns are conducted, especially with the widespread adoption of social media platforms.

These platforms have redefined the methods by which political candidates and parties engage with voters, providing a direct, interactive, and often unfiltered means of communication that bypasses traditional media gatekeepers (Chadwick, 2013; Enli, 2017; Bradshaw & Howard, 2018; Bail, Argyle, Brown & Chen, 2018; González-Bailón, Binns & Salgado, 2020; Arijenwa & Nwaoboli, 2023). Social media platforms such as Facebook, X (formerly Twitter), Instagram and TikTok have become vital tools in shaping public discourse, mobilising voters, and crafting political narratives that resonate

with different segments of the electorate. These perspectives underscore a pivotal moment in political communication, where social media platforms have become essential tools in modern election campaigns. The integration of digital platforms into the electoral process marks a significant shift from traditional media and face-to-face campaigning methods, such as television and radio, towards a more immediate, interactive, and often personalised form of communication. This transformation offers new opportunities for political candidates to reach voters directly, bypassing traditional gatekeepers and fostering a level of engagement that was once unthinkable.

Furthermore, framing on social media can be understood as a mechanism that influences how voters perceive candidates, parties, and political issues. For example, during election campaigns, social media content can frame a candidate as charismatic, relatable, or trustworthy, while at the same time, it can present their opponents as dishonest, unqualified, or out of touch with voters' concerns (Fraser, 2018; Arijenwa & Asemah, 2023). This form of political communication on social media is distinct from traditional forms of campaigning in its interactivity and immediacy. Voters themselves can actively participate in the framing process by commenting, sharing, or even creating their own content, which in turn amplifies or diminishes specific frames. This participatory nature of social media has turned the electorate into a more active participant in the campaign process, enabling the spread of both positive and negative political messages in ways that can either reinforce or challenge existing perceptions (Graham, Broersma, Hazelhoff & van't Haar, 2013).

Moreover, the rise of fake news and misinformation, which often spreads rapidly through social media channels, further complicates the relationship between framing and voter perception. The fluid nature of information on social media makes it easier for false or misleading frames to circulate widely, potentially distorting voters' understanding of key political issues and candidates (Friggeri, Gallotti & Adamic, 2014; Lutz, 2020; Santas & Asemah, 2021; Ajokpeoghene, Pepple & Asemah, 2023). Political campaigns may exploit this vulnerability by spreading misinformation or disinformation, either to discredit opponents or to bolster their own position (Lazer, Baum, Benkler, Berinsky, Greenhill, Menczer & Watts, 2018). The framing of these narratives—whether true or false—can deeply influence voters' opinions and decisions, raising ethical questions about the responsibility of political campaigns, social media platforms, and the electorate itself in maintaining the integrity of the democratic process.

Furthermore, given the centrality of social media in modern electoral campaigns, it is crucial to understand not only how political campaigns use framing strategies to influence voter perceptions but also how voters themselves perceive and interpret these frames. However, the perspective of the electorate, particularly in terms of how they understand and respond to framed content on social media, remains underexplored. In light of these considerations, this study seeks to examine the social media framing of the 2024 gubernatorial elections in Edo State.

Statement of the Problem

The rise of social media as a dominant platform for political discourse has fundamentally transformed how electoral campaigns are conducted and how the electorate engages with political processes. Despite the growing importance of social media in modern elections, the influence of social media framing on electoral outcomes, particularly in the context of Edo gubernatorial elections, remains underexplored. Previous studies have focused on general social media impacts on elections (Asemah, 2017; Arijeniwa & Nwaoboli, 2023; IseOlorunkanmi, Olanrewaju, Oduola, Nweke-Love, Kodi & Akinojo 2023; Elem, Kingsley & Umoke, 2024; Ehiedu, 2024), but specific research on how social media frames gubernatorial election campaigns, particularly in Edo State, is limited. This research gap is particularly critical considering the growing reliance on social media by political parties, candidates and voters in Nigeria's electoral processes. Social media platforms such as Facebook, X (formerly Twitter), Instagram and WhatsApp have become vital tools in reaching voters, particularly in urban areas like Benin City, where digital engagement is increasingly prevalent (Arijeniwa & Nwaoboli, 2023; Nweke, 2023; Sunday, Erude & Aliogo, 2023; Edoja, Ogerugba, Etadafe, Eseimieghan, Iloduba & Erhenede, 2023; Ezegwu, Ezeji, Chukwuemeka & Chime-Nganya, 2024). However, the extent to which these platforms frame the election and how such frames influenced voter perceptions, remains unclear. Therefore, the question arises: what are the frames used in the 2024 Edo gubernatorial election campaign on social media?

Research Objectives

The objective of this study is to:

1. Examine the framing of the 2024 Edo gubernatorial election campaign on social media.

Theoretical Framework

Framing theory, originating from the fields of communication and sociology, focuses on the way media frames or structures information to shape how individuals interpret and understand particular issues, events or topics (Entman, 1993). The major thrust of the theory lies in the understanding that media do not just transmit information, but actively construct and filter it through frames that highlight certain aspects, while downplaying others (Iyengar, 1991). Framing theory also posits that frames are not only embedded in media content, but are also shaped by broader societal, political and cultural factors. These external influences, such as political ideologies, economic structures and journalistic practices, play a crucial role in determining which frames are adopted and propagated in the media (Gamson & Modigliani, 1989; Scheufele, 1999).

Framing theory is particularly relevant to this study because it allows for an exploration of how political messages on social media are structured and presented to the electorate. In the context of the 2024 Edo State governorship election, electorate will

likely employ different frames to emphasise certain aspects of their preferred candidate or party, such as their competence, trustworthiness, or policies.

Understanding Social Media

Social media are widely regarded as a set of digital platforms and applications that facilitate communication and interaction between users (Asemah & Edegoh, 2013; Boyd, 2014; Santas & Asemah, 2021). According to Asemah, Nkwam-Uwaoma, Kente & Amah (2024), social media platforms are digital channel for communication that allows for widespread dissemination of information and interaction with a broader audience. Arijeniwa & Asemah (2024) add that these platforms allow users to create profiles, connect with others and share various forms of content and interaction. These platforms enable the exchange of information, ideas and content through posts, comments and direct messages, fostering a sense of virtual community.

More so, Asemah, Nwaoboli & Nwoko (2022) opined that social media allow for the integration of digital media such as electronic texts, images, moving pictures and music into a well-organised digital environment that allows people to interact with the data for appropriate reasons. Another perspective of social media highlights the centrality of user-generated content in its structure. Therefore, it can be seen that social media is a multifaceted phenomenon that can be understood from various perspectives, whether as a communication tool, a marketing device, a platform for information sharing, or an arena for political engagement.

Election Campaign: An Overview

Elections are central to democratic systems, allowing the public to have a say in the political leadership and policies that will guide the nation. This process ensures accountability and legitimacy for governments, as elected officials derive their authority from the will of the people. Election campaigns are set of political strategies designed to influence voter behaviour and secure electoral victory (Arijeniwa & Nwaoboli, 2023). Campaigns involve analysing voter demographics, targeting key constituencies, and crafting messages that resonate with specific segments of the electorate. The effectiveness of a campaign is often judged by its ability to shape public opinion and drive voter turnout in favour of a candidate or party. Finally, an election campaign is sometimes defined as a form of political marketing, where candidates or political parties brand themselves to appeal to voters (Kotler & Kotler, 2016). This definition likens political campaigns to corporate marketing strategies, where the objective is to build a recognisable image, create emotional connections with voters, and ultimately persuade them to vote for the candidate. Campaigns use modern marketing techniques such as data analytics and targeted messaging to optimise voter engagement. Therefore, election campaigns are recognised as vital tools for mobilisation, persuasion, and the management of public opinion, reflecting the increasingly sophisticated ways in which political actors engage with voters.

Role of Social Media in Political Campaigns

The rise of social media has significantly changed political campaigning, offering politicians unprecedented ways to engage with voters, influence public discourse and gain support. Platforms like Facebook, X (formerly Twitter), Instagram, WhatsApp, TikTok and YouTube are now essential tools for real-time communication, enabling campaigns to reach voters quickly and effectively (Arijeniwa & Nwaoboli, 2023; Egbulefu, Ayeni & Nwaoboli, 2023). Social media's biggest contribution is its ability to create direct communication between politicians and voters. Unlike traditional media, which relied on one-way communication, social media enables two-way conversations (Chadwick, 2013; Arijeníwà & Asemah, 2024). Politicians can engage in real-time exchanges with constituents, addressing concerns instantly. For instance, political figures can use X to respond to breaking news or controversies, directly shaping public opinion.

Social media has also been crucial in engaging younger voters, a demographic that traditionally has lower election turnout (Loader, Vromen & Xenos, 2014; Asemah, 2017). Studies show that social media encourages political discussions, increases participation, and raises awareness of key issues, often inspiring online supporters to take part in offline activism, such as rallies and volunteer work (Boulianne, 2015; Asemah, 2017). Another key feature is the ability to target voters with personalised messages through data analytics, allowing campaigns to deliver tailored ads based on factors like age, location, and interests (Tufekci, 2017; Arijeniwa & Nwaoboli, 2023). The 2016 U.S. presidential election, for example, demonstrated how social media platforms could be used for micro-targeting through Facebook's ad tools (Zengler, 2017). However, this has raised concerns about privacy, ethics, and the regulation of political advertising (González-Bailón, Binns & Salgado, 2020). The spread of fake news and misinformation on social media has prompted calls for stricter regulation of platform owners (Bradshaw & Howard, 2018; Ajokpeoghene et al., 2023). Balancing free speech with preventing harmful content remains a challenge, as social media's algorithms often amplify content that aligns with users' existing views, deepening political polarisation (Bail et al., 2018). In summary, while social media has reshaped political campaigns by providing powerful tools for voter engagement, targeting and mobilisation, it has also raised concerns about misinformation, political division and the ethics of micro-targeting. As social media evolves, it is crucial to balance democratic engagement with protecting political discourse integrity.

Review of Empirical Studies

Arijeniwa & Nwaoboli (2023) examined the impact of social media on election campaigns and political participation among Nigerian youths. The study was anchored on the agenda-setting theory to test its applicability in the context of social media. The objectives included analysing the role of social media in promoting political parties and aspirants during election campaigns and assessing its agenda-setting function on political issues. A survey method was used, with a sample of 400 youths selected through

convenience sampling in Benin City. The findings showed that social media played a significant role in promoting political aspirants and shaping political discussions in Nigeria, especially as the 2023 elections approached. The study concluded that social media was effective in influencing political participation but recommended that users verify political information before sharing. Additionally, political parties were advised to avoid spreading falsehoods during their campaigns. Arijeniwa & Nwaoboli's (2023) did not delve into the specific framing strategies used in social media to encourage or discourage participation. The present study addressed the framing aspect, particularly how different political narratives and messages are constructed in the 2024 Edo State Gubernatorial campaigns.

Egbulefu *et al* (2023) analysed social media netizens' responses to the 2023 "Obidient" campaign in Nigeria. Its primary objectives were to assess the extent of social media use in Peter Obi's campaign, determine the tone of netizens' responses, and examine the impact of these responses. Erving Goffman's 1974 framing theory was used as the theoretical framework. A qualitative textual analysis was applied, using multi-stage sampling to select Facebook as the platform for the study. The findings revealed that social media netizens widely portrayed Peter Obi as a competent leader, emphasising his ability to unite the country and bring positive change. The study concluded that while social media played a key role in rallying support for Obi, efforts to reach rural and semi-rural areas with low internet penetration were necessary to ensure wider campaign success. The study recommended that the Obidient movement intensify offline efforts, especially in less connected regions. Egbulefu *et al* (2023) did not explicitly examine how these campaigns are framed on social media. The present study explored the specific framing techniques of voters in Edo State.

Nweke (2023) evaluated the influence of social media on undergraduate students' political choices at the University of Benin during the 2023 general election. The rationale was to explore the role of social media in shaping political preferences among Nigerian youths. The theoretical framework combined the media equation theory and vale's persuasion theory. A survey method was employed, with 398 undergraduate students surveyed through questionnaire. The findings revealed that social media significantly influenced the political choices of students, with many seeing it as a vital tool for political engagement. The study concluded that social media positively impacted students' political awareness and engagement. The researchers recommended that political parties and governmental bodies establish a strong social media presence to educate and engage the youth demographic. Nweke (2023) did not look at specific frames; the present research focused specifically on framing—how social media presents and shapes political information—rather than just influence on candidate choice.

Sunday *et al* (2023) examined the relevance and impact of social media on elections in Nigeria, with a focus on the 2020 gubernatorial election in Edo State. The study was grounded in Max Weber's Theory of Social Action, which explains the impact of both external (institutional) and internal (personal factors) variables on voter behaviour.

A mixed-method approach was used, with both qualitative and quantitative data collection through surveys. The findings revealed that social media played a crucial role in the election, especially among younger voters. The study concluded that social media's influence on elections in Nigeria cannot be overstated; recommending that the government enhance digital literacy and develop targeted strategies based on demographic factors. Sunday *et al* (2023) focused on the 2020 election; the present study focused on the 2024 election, thus providing current insights into the evolving role of social media in shaping electoral perceptions and political discourse.

Omachi, Oluwafisayo & Ezegwu (2023) explored public opinion on the effectiveness of the "Obidients" social media campaigns for Peter Obi during the 2023 Nigerian presidential election. The objectives were to evaluate the extent of the campaign, identify the platforms used, and assess its effectiveness in mobilising support. The theoretical framework was based on the Uses and Gratification theory. A survey research design was adopted, using questionnaires for data collection. The findings showed that the "Obidients" effectively used social media, particularly WhatsApp, to promote Obi's candidacy and engage with potential voters. The researchers concluded that social media played a critical role in political campaigning and recommended that political actors focus on understanding the preferences of their audience, especially on popular platforms like WhatsApp. Omachi *et al* (2023) focused on a single campaign's social media strategy, the present study takes a broader approach and explored how campaigns are framed across platforms.

Methodology

The researchers used the dialectical hermeneutic method of textual analysis. This approach of textual analysis is utilised when researchers wish to provide in-depth description and explanation of fundamental structures expressed in a media text (Ekhareafo & Umoro, 2020; Asemah, Gujbawu, Ekhareafo & Okpanachi, 2022). The textual analysis method was employed to gather textual materials from selected social media platforms. The textual analysis was thematised to enhance coding and analysed to extract meaningful interpretations from the data. The population covered social media posts on the 2024 Edo governorship elections from select social media platforms (Facebook and X) posted between January 1st and September 20th, 2024. A Facebook and X search for the term “#EdoGubernatorialElection2024 and #EdoDecides2024” on January 20, 2024 came up with 138 stories on Facebook while X came up 156 tweets respectively; hence, the population is 294. To collect samples, the purposive sampling technique was employed to choose 20 posts with the highest comments on *Facebook* and *X*. Thus, ten (10) posts each were drawn from the many posts on Facebook and tweets on X; thus, making the total sampled contents twenty (20). These comments were thematised and evaluated based on the following themes: Negative campaigning, Battle for Edo Future, Praise Singing, Candidates' Critics, Contest between Political policies and ideologies.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Negative Campaigning

Excerpt Text 1:

Source: Facebook

Excerpt Text 2:

Source: Facebook

Excerpt Text 3:

Source: X

Excerpt Text 4:

Source: X

Excerpt 1, 2, 3 and 4 suggest that the social media framing of the 2024 Edo gubernatorial election showed that the social media users engaged in negative campaigning. Excerpt 1, 2 3, and 4 focused on the reputation of the candidates of APC, PDP and LP respectively in order to undermine their credibility and highlight their weaknesses.

Battle for Edo Future

Excerpt Text 5:

Source: Facebook

Excerpt Text 6:

Source: Facebook

Excerpt Text 7:

Source: X

Excerpt Text 8:

Source: X

Excerpt 5, 6, 7 and 8 suggest that the social media framing of the 2024 Edo gubernatorial election showed that the social media users engaged in a battle for Edo. Excerpt 5 and 6 framed the election as what Edo desires, stating that Edo wants APC and PDP respectively while Excerpt 7 and 8 reminded the Edo people the importance of the election to the State.

Praise Singing

Excerpt Text 9:

Source: Facebook

Excerpt Text 10:

Source: Facebook

Excerpt Text 11:

Source: X

Excerpt Text 12:

Source: X

Excerpt 9, 10, 11 and 12 suggest that the social media framing of the 2024 Edo gubernatorial election showed that the social media users engaged in praise singing of the candidates. Excerpt 9 and 10 praised the candidate of PDP, Asue Ighodalo while Excerpt 11 focused on the candidate of the LP, Olumide Akpata and Excerpt 12 praised the APC candidate.

Candidates' Critics

Excerpt Text 13:

Source: Facebook

Excerpt Text 14

Source: Facebook

Excerpt Text 15:

Source: X

Excerpt Text 16:

Source: X

Excerpt 13, 14, 15 and 16 suggest that the social media framing of the 2024 Edo gubernatorial election showed that the social media users engaged criticisms of the candidates. Excerpt 13 criticised the candidate of LP about his choice of a Yoruba name “Olumide” as against his Edo name, “Osaigbovo,” while Excerpt 14 criticised the candidates of APC and PDP who are both of Esan extraction, noting that being born of Esan father does not make them Esan Indigenes. Specifically, Excerpt 15 and 16 criticised the candidates of APC and their candidate’s, Monday Okpebholo, intellectual and intelligence respectively.

Contest between Political Policies and Ideologies

Excerpt Text 17:

Source: Facebook

Excerpt Text 18:

Source: Facebook

Excerpt Text 19:

Source: X

Excerpt Text 20:

Source: X

The direction of comments and tweets in excerpts 17, 18, 19 and 20 all points to the fact that the social media users were framing the election along policy and ideological lines. This suggests that the framing social media of the 2024 Edo gubernatorial election was policy and ideological-based.

Discussion of Findings

This study aimed to examine the framing of the 2024 Edo gubernatorial election campaign on social media. The data from the textual analysis excerpts 1-20 provide a nuanced view of the frames used during the 2024 Edo gubernatorial election campaign on social media. The analysis of the excerpts highlights the various ways social media users framed the election, influencing how candidates and their platforms were perceived. These frames are categorised into five main themes: negative campaigning, battle for Edo's future, praise singing, candidates' critics and contest between political policies and ideologies.

Excerpts 1, 2, 3 and 4 demonstrate the prevalence of negative campaigning on social media during the election. These posts focused on undermining the credibility of the candidates from the APC, PDP and LP, attacking their reputations and highlighting

perceived weaknesses. The framing here sought to discredit opponents and sway public opinion by emphasising their faults and vulnerabilities. This tactic of negative campaigning has been shown to be effective in electoral politics, as it directs attention away from the candidates' strengths and forces voters to consider their weaknesses. This approach aligns with findings from Omachi *et al* (2023) who observed how social media campaigns during the 2023 presidential election used negative framing to polarise public opinion and detract from candidates' positive attributes. Furthermore, this framing is indicative of the Framing Theory, where media outlets and social media users can actively shape public perception by framing issues or candidates in a negative light.

Excerpts 5, 6, 7 and 8 shifted the focus towards a framing that portrayed the election as a critical battle for the future of Edo State. These posts framed the election in terms of what the people of Edo desired, with excerpts 5 and 6 arguing that the state wanted either the APC or PDP to govern, while excerpts 7 and 8 reminded voters of the importance of their vote and the dire consequences of not choosing wisely. This frame tapped into the public sphere theory, where social media serves as a space for public deliberation and discourse. The battle for the state's future is framed as a collective decision, with voters urged to participate in shaping the direction of their community. The idea of social media acting as a forum for public discussion aligns with Arijeniwa & Nwaoboli (2023), who noted the significant role of social media in promoting political participation and the shaping of political discussions.

In contrast to negative campaigning, excerpts 9, 10, 11 and 12 highlighted praise singing, where social media users expressed admiration for specific candidates, particularly those from the PDP, LP and APC. These excerpts framed the candidates in a positive light, emphasising their strengths, qualities and potential to lead the state effectively. Praise singing is a common tactic used in political campaigns to build a favourable public image of a candidate. It can encourage voter support and increase the perceived legitimacy of a candidate. This frame reflects Egbulefu *et al* (2023)'s findings on the "Obidient" campaign, where social media was used to project Peter Obi as a competent leader capable of bringing positive change, thereby aligning with framing techniques that emphasise positive attributes and qualities. This approach ties into Framing Theory, as it involves shaping the perception of the candidates through carefully constructed positive narratives.

Excerpts 13, 14, 15 and 16 present another critical frame, where social media users openly criticised the candidates. These critiques targeted specific aspects of the candidates' identities, such as their names (Excerpts 13 and 14), their intellectual capabilities (Excerpts 15 and 16) and their backgrounds. Such criticisms sought to challenge the authenticity and suitability of the candidates, thus influencing voters' perceptions. This type of framing engages with the framing theory by selectively highlighting negative attributes or weaknesses that may cause doubt about a candidate's suitability for office. Similar to negative campaigning, this frame leverages flaws to create doubt, making it a powerful tool in electoral discourse. It also reflects findings

from Sunday *et al* (2023), who noted the impact of social media in shaping voters' perceptions and influencing electoral choices.

Excerpts 17, 18, 19 and 20 reflect a final frame that centred on political policies and ideologies. The discussion on these platforms focused on the political policies proposed by the candidates, as well as the ideological lines that defined their respective parties. This frame positioned the election as a contest between competing visions for the future of Edo State, with social media users engaging in discussions about which candidate's policies were most suitable for addressing the state's challenges. This framing of the election along policy and ideological lines reflects the importance of informing voters about the substance behind political campaigns. This approach is consistent with Nweke (2023), who found that social media played a significant role in informing and influencing the political choices of university students by engaging them in policy discussions. The framing of the election based on policy and ideology aligns well with the public sphere theory, where social media provides a platform for informed public deliberation on the political issues at stake.

Thus, the social media frames during the 2024 Edo gubernatorial election campaign were diverse and multifaceted. From negative campaigning to praise singing, from critiques of candidates to the emphasis on political policies and ideologies, these frames played a crucial role in shaping the electorate's views. The findings align with framing theory, as the strategic use of language, images, and narratives in these frames worked to influence voter perceptions and decisions.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study highlighted the prominence of social media platforms in the election campaign, especially *Facebook* and *X*, which were central to the dissemination of campaign messages. These platforms not only served as spaces for information sharing but also as battlegrounds for political discourse, where various frames, including negative campaigning and ideological debates, shaped voters' understanding of the election. In line with the foregoing, the following recommendations are made:

1. Political parties and political campaigns organisers should focus on framing issues and candidates in a positive and constructive light, prioritising policy discussions over personal attacks. Negative campaigning should be avoided in favour of highlighting candidates' qualifications and their plans for the future of Edo State.
2. Social media platforms and political campaigns teams should work together to address the concerns of voters regarding the accuracy and bias of election-related content. This can be achieved by ensuring the use of fact-checking mechanisms and encouraging transparency in campaign messaging.

References

- Ajibulu, O. A. & Asemah, E. S. (2021). Contributions of social media to the mobilisation of youth for the 2020 EndSARS protest in Nigeria. In E. S. Asemah (Ed.). *Communication, Pandemic and Civil Unrest in Nigeria* (pp. 231-239). Enugu: Franklead Press.
- Ajokpeoghene, J. Pepple, I. I. & Asemah, E. S. (2023). Fake news as an impediment to media development in Nigeria. In E.S. Asemah (ed.), *Mass Media, Politics and Civic Engagement in Nigeria* (pp.116-125). Jos: Jos University Press.
- Arijeniwa, A.F. & Nwaoboli, E.P. (2023). Setting agenda for public discourse: Examining the impact of social media on political participation amongst Nigerian youth. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Approach and Studies*, 10(1), 36-53.
- Aríjeníwà, A.F. & Asemah, E. S. (2024). Benin residents' perception of the influence of social media on the commodification of indigenous cultures in Nigeria. *Biannual Review of Glorious Vision University*, 1(1), 86-101.
- Asemah, E. S., Nwaoboli, E. P. & Nwoko, Q. T. (2022). Textual analysis of select social media hate speech messages against Clergymen in Nigeria. *GVU Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, 7(2), 1-14.
- Asemah, E. S. & Edegoh, L. O. N. (2013). Social media and insecurity in Nigeria: A critical appraisal. In D, Wilson (Ed). *Communication and Social Media in Nigeria: Social Engagements, Political Developments and Public Discourse*. Lagos: ACCE.
- Asemah, E. S., Gujbawu, M., Ekharefo, D. O. & Okpanachi, R. A. (2022). *Research methods and procedures in mass communication (3rd. Ed.)*. Jos: Great Future Press.
- Asemah, E. S. (2017). Use of social media in the 2015 presidential elections in Nigeria. *The Mass Communicator: An International Journal of Communication*, 11(3), 4-11.
- Asemah, E. S., Nwammuo, A. N. & Nkwam-Uwaoma, A. O. A. (2022). *Theories and models of communication (2nd Ed.)*. Jos: Jos University Press.
- Asemah, E.S., Nkwam-Uwaoma, A. O., Kente. J. S. & Amah, F. O. (2024). *International communication in a globalised village*. Jos: Jos University Press
- Bail, C. A., Argyle, L. P., Brown, T. W. & Chen, H. (2018). Exposure to opposing views on social media can increase political polarisation. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 115(37), 9216-9221.
- Boulianne, S. (2015). Social media use and participation: A meta-analysis of current research. *Information, Communication and Society*, 18(5), 524-538.
- Bradshaw, S. & Howard, P. N. (2018). The global organisation of the political advertising business: A comparative analysis of the 2016 US and UK elections. *Journal of Information Technology and Politics*, 15(3), 1-20.
- Chadwick, A. (2013). *The hybrid media system: Politics and power*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Edoja, E., Ogerugba, I., Etadafe, C. K., Eseimieghan, S., Iloduba, L. N. & Erhenede, A. (2023). Public perception of the role of the mass media in communicating the 2023 electoral process: a study of the gubernatorial elections in Delta State. *Journal of Global Social Sciences*, 4(16), 187 - 213.

- Egbulefu, C. C., Ayeni, A. A. & Nwaoboli, E. P. (2023). Textual analysis of social media netizens response to the 2023 “Obidient” campaigns in Nigeria. *Wellspring University Journal of Social and Management Sciences*, 2(1), pp. 14-26.
- Egwa, A., Obaje, C. E. & Asemah, E. S. (2024). Edo state residents’ perception of broadcast media reportage of the use of bimodal voter accreditation system during 2023 Nigerian presidential election. *International Journal of Sub-Saharan African Research (IJSSAR)*, 2(4). 223-239.
- Ehiedu, M. C. (2024). Social media political advertising and its influence on voters’ choice of candidates in Benin during the 2023 presidential elections. Unpublished Bachelor of Arts degree project, Department of Mass Communication, University of Benin, Nigeria.
- Elem, E. O, Kingsley, E. O. & Umoke, C. E. (2024). Political parties and the matrix of social media war in Nigeria. *African Journal of Politics and Administrative Studies (AJPAS)*, 17(1), 832-856.
- Enli, G. (2017). *Social Media and political participation: The case of political polarisation*. London: Routledge.
- Enli, G. (2017). Twitter as a political tool: The use of social media in the 2011 and 2015 Norwegian elections. *Media, Culture & Society*, 39(5), 702-718.
- Entman, R. M. (1993). Framing: Toward clarification of a fractured paradigm. *Journal of Communication*, 43(4), 51-58.
- Ezegwu, D. T., Ezeji, A. O., Chukwuemeka, G. N. & Chime-Nganya, C. R. (2024). Abuja residents’ perception of mass media coverage of the 2023 presidential election campaign in Nigeria. *Wukari International Studies Journal*, 8(5), 134-144.
- Fraser, C. (2018). Media, power and the framing of political events. *Political Communication Review*, 18(3), 122-145.
- Friggeri, A., Gallotti, R. & Adamic, L. A. (2014). Rumor Cascades. *Proceedings of the 2014 ACM Conference on Computer Supported Cooperative Work*, 31-40.
- Gamson, W. A. & Modigliani, A. (1989). Media discourse and public opinion on nuclear power: A constructionist approach. *American Journal of Sociology*, 95(1), 1-37.
- González-Bailón, S., Binns, R. & Salgado, S. (2020). Social media and democracy: The state of the field and prospects for research. *Political Communication*, 37(3), 385-402.
- Graham, T., Broersma, M., Hazelhoff, K. & van't Haar, G. (2013). Between broadcasting and blogging: A hybrid model of political communication. *Information, Communication & Society*, 16(5), 7-14.
- IseOlorunkanmi, O.J., Olanrewaju, A.F., Oduola, J.O., Nweke-Love, H.C., Kodi, E.E. & Akinojo, I.C. (2023). The influence of social media on political communication: A case study of Nigeria's 2023 general elections in Omu-Aran. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research*, 9(7), 31-46.
- Iyengar, S. (1991). *Is anyone responsible? How television frames political issues*. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press.
- Kotler, P. & Kotler, N. (2016). *Marketing for non-profit organisations*. New York: Pearson Prentice Hall.

- Lazer, D. M. J., Baum, M. A., Benkler, Y., Berinsky, A. J., Greenhill, K. M., Menczer, F. & Watts, D. J. (2018). The science of fake news. *Science*, 359(6380), 1094-1096.
- Loader, B. D., Vromen, A. & Xenos, M. A. (2014). *The networked young citizen: Social media, political participation and civic engagement*. London: Routledge.
- Lutz, M. (2020). Misinformation and democracy in the digital age: The impact of fake news on Nigerian elections. *Media, Culture & Society*, 42(4), pp. 564-580.
- Nweke, I. J. (2023). Influence of social media political campaign on the choice of candidates among the undergraduates of university of Benin in the 2023 general election. Unpublished Bachelor of Arts Degree Project, Department of Mass Communication, University of Benin, Nigeria.
- Oladele, V. I. & Asemah, E. S. (2022). Digital democracy as panacea to Nigeria's ailing electoral and democratic institutions. In E. S. Asemah., D. O. Ekhareafu & T. Santas (Eds.). *Thoughts on Political Communication in Nigeria*. Jos: University Press.
- Olaoye, G. T., Enyindah, S. C. & Asemah, E. S. (2022). Influence of politics today on channels television on public opinion about politics in Benin, Edo State, Nigeria. In E. S. Asemah., D. O. Ekhareafu & T. Santas (Eds.). *Thoughts on Political Communication in Nigeria*. Jos: University Press.
- Omoevah, B. A. Oladele., O. O. & Asemah, E. S. (2022). Coverage of Anambra state governorship election in select Nigerian newspapers. In E. S. Asemah., D. O. Ekhareafu & T. Santas (Eds.). *Thoughts on Political Communication in Nigeria*. Jos: University Press.
- Santas, T., Asemah, E. S. & Jumbo, C. N. (2020). Mass media and the mobilisation of women for political participation during the 2019 gubernatorial election in Lafia, Nigeria. *The Nigerian Journal of Communication*, 17(2), 199-217.
- Santas, T. & Asemah, E. S. (2021). A discourse on the implications of social media fake news on Nigeria's democracy. In E. S. Asemah & P. R. Obuko'adata (Eds.), *Communication and Meta-Communication: A Discourse in Media and Society*. Jos: University Press.
- Scheufele, D. A. (1999). Framing as a theory of media effects. *Journal of Communication*, 49(1), pp.103-122.
- Sunday, V., Erude, S. U. & Aliogo, R. N. (2023). The Impact of social media on Elections in Nigeria: An Assessment of 2020 Gubernatorial Election in Edo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Political Science and Leadership Research*, 9(3), 201-226.
- Tufekci, Z. (2017). *Twitter and tear gas: The power and fragility of networked protest*. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press.
- Zengler, T. (2017). The Trump campaign's use of big data in the 2016 election. *Harvard Business Review*, 3, 60-77.